

Mechanisms of Master Data Quality: The Case of an Enterprise System Implementation

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Abstract. The causes of master data quality issues that continue to negatively affect the implementation of Enterprise Systems (ES) are unknown. This paper identifies mechanisms as precursors of master data quality issues. Critical Realism was used as the research paradigm and Affordance Theory as a lens. A case study of an ES implementation at a university was undertaken where two mechanisms, a gatekeeping and a silo mechanism, emerged as precursors of master data quality. By uncovering these mechanisms, future ES implementations could improve collaboration and reduce post implementation support.

Keywords: Affordance Theory, Critical Realism, Data Quality, Enterprise System, Master Data, Mechanism.

Introduction

Data is as fundamental to an organization as code is to its core software applications [1] where the explosive growth of data brings unprecedented prospects for decision making and growth [2], and pressure to make timely and accurate decisions [3]. Yet, there is often insufficient trust in organizational data to generate reports and confidently make decisions [4]. Data Quality (DQ) has the greatest impact on how data is valued, such that the higher the DQ is, the more value the data has [5]. DQ has become one of the most prevalent challenges for organizations aiming to realize process efficiency [6].

Master data is important, relatively static, organization-wide data about main entities, that are core to business processes [7] and important in creating one version of the truth in Enterprise Systems (ES) [8]. ES are large-scale packaged software applications that integrate integral business processes [9]. ES implementations are risky, where 40 to 60 percent of them fail [10], often because of poor DQ [11]. Master data quality (MDQ) combines the concepts of master data and DQ [12]. Definitions for DQ revolve around two themes, firstly the extent to which data meets requirements and secondly, if it is fit for use or purpose [13]. Hence, MDQ refers to fundamental, relatively static data that is accurate, fit for use and meets organizational requirements. There has been limited research investigating the critical success factors for high MDQ [14] or guidelines on how to manage MDQ requirements [15]; or theories about it [6]. Further research into the precursors of MDQ issues has been recommended [16].

Hence the research question asked is: What mechanisms lead to MDQ issues across ES? This research used Critical Realism (CR) and Affordance Theory [17] to analyze data collected from a case study of an ES implementation. Next, we present a literature review, then the methodology that elucidates CR and Affordance Theory followed by a case description. Findings from the data analysis of the case are discussed before concluding with insights into the uncovered mechanisms and how they could contribute to further knowledge around precursors of MDQ.

Literature Review

A literature review in a prior paper presented precursors of MDQ issues in ES identified in 56 relevant publications between January 2013 – May 2024 [16] using the eight step method by Okoli [18] and the Work Systems Framework (WSF) that comprises nine elements: *Processes and Activities*; *Participants*; *Information*; *Technologies Products/Services*; *Customers*; *Environment*; and *Infrastructure and Strategies*. The first four are internal, and the latter five are external to the work system [19]. *Processes and activities* from the literature consisted of five codes in order of prevalence: *Increase in complexity*; *Inefficient organizational processes*; *Manual data capturing*; *Deadlines and timelines*; and *Inadequate application of business rules*. *Participants* had eight codes namely: *Skills of the users*, *Lack of a global understanding of data or processes across an organization*; *Lack of data ownership*; *Organizational Silos*; *Need for Management Support*; *Resource constraints*; *Organizational structure challenges*; and *User Participation*. *Information* included four codes that occurred frequently throughout the literature: *Source Data Issues*; *Increasing Data Volumes*; *Insufficient Naming, Data Standards, Classification or Semantics*; and *Intangibility of Data*. *Technologies* had two codes: *Inadequate Technological Infrastructure*; and *Lack of Data Management Automation*. *Products/services* had one code: *Data Analysis and Reporting Requirements*. *Customers* had one code which was *Incorrect Information from Self-reporting*. *Environment* included six codes; *Organizational Customers and Culture*; *Lack of Importance Given to DQ*; *Ineffective Communication*; *Lack of, or Unclear, Roles and Responsibilities*; *Need for Institutional Knowledge*; and *Organizational Size*. *Infrastructure* contains three codes: *Data from Disparate Sources*; *Technical Silos*; and *Increase in Software Applications*. *Strategies* included three codes: *Lack of Data Governance*; *Lack of Strategic Alignment* and *Lack of Data Management Strategy*.

Yet it is not clear what underlying mechanisms are generating these precursors, why they still occur after being identified, and what connections between the issues are. An issue like the *Need for management support* could be linked to *Lack of data governance* and may or may not be caused by the same mechanism. Geographically, there was one paper relating to DQ issues in Africa [20] and three papers based on university case studies [15, 20, 21], making an African University (AU) suitable to widen the body of research and understand the mechanisms behind the precursors of MDQ issues and possible connections between issues.

Method

CR claims that there is an independent, external world existing separately from our perceptions that we can investigate to attain knowledge, but we need to be aware of the inescapably imperfect nature of that knowledge in the context in which it occurs [22]. CR entails searching for mechanisms [17]. There are three nested domains of CR: mechanisms emerge from social and physical structures of the *Real* domain and are the intrinsic properties in an entity or structure that cause forces to create events to eventually appear at the *Empirical* domain [23]; the *Actual* domain is a subdomain of the *Real* that includes events emerging from the mechanisms [24]; the *Empirical* domain, as a subdomain of the *Actual* and the *Real*, is where events occur as we experience them [23]. Affordance Theory assists in practically identifying mechanisms [25].

Affordance is a lens used to theorize the relationship between users and technology that, in this context, would be the relationship between an artifact and a goal-oriented actor, with the capabilities latent in the environment, associated with achieving an immediate concrete outcome emerging from that relationship [26]. Affordances that emerge can result in good MDQ, yet the actual outcome, is unknown, because, although there is the potential for the desired action, there is a socio-technical context existing that can affect the outcome [17]. Six steps were followed to apply Affordance Theory in CR data analysis: 1. Identification and Description of Events and Issues; 2. Identification of Key Entities and Associations; 3. Abduction (Theoretical Re-description); 4. Retroduction (Identification and Selection of Candidate Affordances); 5. Analyzing Affordances and Associated Mechanisms; and 6. Assessing Explanatory Power [17].

Case studies are a relevant means to identify mechanisms when using CR [22]. A researcher can be an active participant in CR research [27]. In this case, the first author was on the implementation team. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 key stakeholders involved with the ES implementation. Interviews were recorded, transcribed and coded via thematic analysis in Nvivo. The interviewees were given pseudonyms to maintain their anonymity as follows: First Digit: I (Internal to the project team), E (External to the project team); Second Digit: A (Analyst), S (Support), D (Developer), U (Super User), M (Management), C (Researcher/Academic); Third Digit: T (IT Department), R (Central Research), F (Faculty Research), V (Vendor).

The ES implemented at AU was a Research Information System (RIS), simply referred to as RIS. A RIS is a system that harvests, manages and delivers information on research activities and outputs [28]. RIS, also referred to as Research Information Management Systems, Faculty Activity Reporting Systems or Current Research Information Systems, are increasingly being used within research organizations and universities internationally [29]. RIS was implemented to address the growth of research and increasing complexity of research management. The project included the re-calibration of research support, selecting and implementing an appropriate ES. The recalibration started in 2014, and the RIS implementation ran from January 2016 to December 2020. The first module (the Publication Count) was needed to prepare the next government submission for significant publication subsidy and move off the historical system. This involved master data imports from source systems namely: the Human Resources (HR) system for permanent and contract staff master data; a custom third-party system for

ad-hoc, paid on claim staff and vendor master data; a student system for all the student master data; the historical system.

In 2016, the first master data import occurred. Low quality master data flooded RIS, to the point where 25% of the support calls were master data related. As more modules were rolled out, the need for reporting increased and poor MDQ was further exposed. While rolling out modules, the implementation team also supported existing modules, troubleshooting existing MDQ issues. This was challenging and not adequately planned for. When the project ended, MDQ issues remained as post implementation support.

Findings: Mechanisms leading to MDQ Issues

The findings are arranged according to the six steps of Affordance Theory, under the research paradigm of CR. Explanations of each step are now detailed.

Identification and Description of Events and Issues

The process of identifying the events emerged partially from the interviewees and the researchers, according to the approach by Bygstad, et al. [17]. Six events of poor MDQ emerged, mentioned by at least eight interviewees. These are listed in **Table 1** [30] in order of frequency (number of interviews they were mentioned in) along with a summarized description of each event.

Table 1. Timeline and Description of Events.

Time	Count	Event Name	Event Description
2016	20	Initial Master Data Integration from the Source Systems	The initial import of master data from source systems was rushed and poorly planned, with low confidence in the source systems' master data. In the HR system, limited access to data affected the data import.
2017 - 2020	18	Post Implementation Clean-up and Support	After the first module went live and other modules were being implemented which relied on the same master data. Interviewees mentioned unexpected issues like source capturing in silos and missing information.
2016 - 2020	15	Reporting on ES Data	Reports surfaced previously unknown MDQ issues. The reports included submission to the government for subsidy, internal reporting or general reports created outside of RIS.
2016 - 2020	13	Project Implementation of the ES	Issues from the project implementation of RIS included requirements gathering; training of power users; rollout of modules; organizational restructure; and change resistance.
2016	10	Preparing for the Publication Count Module	Actors needed to manually capture data in the ES; the loss of subsidy income from missing master data; and deadlines imposed for report submission.
2018 - 2019	8	Historical Data Migration	There were issues regarding the duplication and mismatch of data from the historical system.

Identification of Key Entities and Associations

Key entities and events from the interview data included human and non-human actors. Core technical objects were mapped diagrammatically in **Fig. 1** and key human actors (as groupings) were identified in **Table 2** [17]. **Fig. 1** shows the flow of master data into RIS from three source systems into the *Data Warehouse* where they merged into an *Integration Table*. One other source was the *Spreadsheet Extract* from the *Historical System*, populated from HR and Finance master data which, although coming from the same ES, was referred to as two different systems. The organizational structure from HR did not work for Finance. The Finance part of the ES was available in the *Data Warehouse* but was rather imported via a *Spreadsheet Extract* into the *Historical System*. The *Government Submission* for subsidy income was intended to be extracted from *RIS* but manual *Data Capture* into *RIS* as well as directly on the *Government Submission* was required. Where staff could not readily get master data, they extracted it from *RIS* and then augmented the data in other *Standalone Spreadsheets*. In **Table 2**, the main human actor groups are listed, with *HR* as most widely mentioned, followed by *Central Research* who sponsored the project, then the *Project Implementation Team* who implement *RIS* and thereafter the *Administrative Faculties* who would be the main contributors to the research activity. In previous studies, affordances were conceptualized at an individual actor level, but they are progressively being studied at a group level [31] as was the approach in this analysis.

Fig. 1. Data Sources into the ES.

Table 2. Human Actors as Organizational Groupings.

Actor Group	Description	Interviews	Count
HR	HR department.	12	113
Central Research	Central Research department sponsoring RIS implementation.	10	143
Project Implementation Team	The team of temporary and permanent staff members implementing RIS.	10	133
Administrative faculties	Administrators from academic faculties.	10	34

Abduction (Theoretical Re-description)

Experience and creativity is required in this step and can be aided by a sensitizing device such as extant theory [17]. An extant theory, Collective Action, specifically, Collective Action problems, was found to explain the issues that arose from the interviews. Collective Action occurs when actors, often in organizations, act together to provide collective goods that could not be achieved individually [32]. Collective Action problems occur when actors take actions that have maximum benefit to themselves but end up with lower shared results than could have been attained [33, 34]. Data Governance (DG) has previously been described as a Collective Action problem encompassing six challenges, namely perceiving value, enabling collaboration; fostering capabilities; data overview; local practices; and political ambience; which is represented diagrammatically in a problem triangle of DG [34]. Since MDQ is core to DG [35], the researchers used the problem triangle of DG to explain the MDQ challenges from the case (Figure 2). Specific examples of occurrences are in **Table 3**.

Fig. 2. The problem triangle of data governance[34], adapted for MDQ.

Table 3. Collective Action Problems.

Challenges	Examples from AU
Perceiving value	The interviewees indicated issues regarding the value placed on the MDQ: “I think a fundamental problem at [AU], and it probably exists in all organisations, is that there was never any awareness of the fact that these critical master data attributes were critical master data attributes.” [IMR01].
Data overview	There was a lack of an overview of master data at the AU: “So, it's actually again, it's more of a, if there's more structure, if the people who may be in a higher level, took more responsibility, and, you know, there's more clarity on why we're capturing things in a different, in a certain way.” [EMR02].
Fostering capabilities	A lack of MDQ skills to deal with MDQ adequately: “Ja, so I would say expertise in terms of understanding the data landscape of the institution, they were not experts” [IAR02].

Challenges	Examples from AU
Local practices	There was an inability to tie the practices needed for RIS to the rest of the university due to silos: “Each silo tended to make its own decisions, which made sense for them, but didn't necessarily make sense for the rest.” [IMR01].
Enabling collaboration	A lack of collaboration to use master data for different functions: “...people capturing in silos ... and therefore capturing different information, or having different levels of quality control.” [EMF01].
Political ambience	Different political interests and gatekeeping of the data: “...it was a definite issue in that there was a split between HR, and HR was never actually, I don't know if they are yet, but they weren't moved into [IT Department] as a department.” [EDT02].

Issues arising from the problem triangle indicated that there were silos that could be bridged via relationships between actors. The researchers explored Social Capital to further explain this phenomenon. Social Capital is the formation of an intangible kind of capital that binds actors, or groups of actors, together via their existing relationships to assist productive activity [36] and has been linked to positive outcomes for individuals and groups [37]. **Fig. 3** shows a network on the left with a lack of closure, and one on the right where closure is present. In the network without closure, actor A has a relationship with actors B and C and can act in an unfavorable manner to B or C because they do not have a relationship with each other (only with actors D or E). Unless the unfavorable action is so bad that B and/or C confronts A independently, A is free to carry on with unfavorable actions. Alternatively, in the network with closure on the right, B and C have ties to each other and can collaborate in confronting A [36]. The authors argue that, in a network without closure, B and D could be in a different silo than C and E. If the system A, was not providing the data that B needed, B would collaborate with D in their siloed department to capture the missing data in a spreadsheet. In a network with closure, B would have formed a relationship with C and could ask them for the data directly. Instead of C capturing the data in A, C would provide this information to B as a once-off extract as a gatekeeper of the information. An example of the lack of closure, the interviewees, regarding requests for missing master data in RIS from HR, stated “The lack of [RIS] would not stop the university from working, therefore, it sat at the bottom of the priority pile.” [IAR04], however, a manager requesting information from departments where they had built relationships indicated “Typically, most of the departments do bend over backwards” [EMR01] to provide master data. In the next step, we use retroduction to explore these concepts further.

Fig. 3. Closure within a Network [36].

Retroduction (Identification and Selection of Candidate Affordances)

There are four sub-steps to retroduction, namely: identification of immediate concrete outcomes, analysis of the interplay of human and technical entities; identification of candidate affordance; and identification of stimulating and releasing conditions [17, 38]. These sub-steps are illustrated in Fig. 4 as Concrete outcome; the oval indicating the double arrow between the actor and the technology; Affordance; and the Stimulating and Releasing arrows respectively. The immediate concrete outcome occurs through the actions of goal-oriented actors [17], the researchers therefore had to investigate how the actors interacted at AU over time. Technological affordances at an organization tend to revolve around standardizing and controlling operations [31]. Two of the affordances that the system provided were compliance and process automation. For all affordances, the *Enabling condition* was *Access to quality master data*, and the Techno-organizational context was the University infrastructure. The main driver for the first roll out was the government report submission for subsidy income. Further modules in RIS were also used to track and regulate grant applications which had their own conditions for compliance via report submission to the funder as well as for internal approval from the university. Both requirements are indicated in the compliance candidate affordance in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Affordance structure [17].

Fig. 5. Candidate Affordance 1: Compliance

To comply with government and funder regulations, accurate reports, as the concrete outcome, needed to be submitted by *Central Research* and the *Administrative Faculties*, as actors. Master data that was taken from the source systems had varying levels of quality. RIS users were faced with the difficult task of either requesting HR actors to change the data; individuals in the Administrative Faculties to change their data; to capture the master data into RIS; or directly onto the spreadsheet that needed to be submitted; as the releasing condition. The second candidate affordance is Process Automation. **Fig. 5.** RIS was intended to streamline and automate research administrative processes for *Central Research* (actor) to be able to manage and enable research administration effectively. They enlisted the assistance of a *Project Implementation Team* (the second actor) to do so. Master data via integration from source systems were used to populate RIS.

Fig. 6. Candidate Affordance 2: Process Automation

To automate processes in RIS, workflows needed to be generated and approvals from various levels of AU were required, however, there wasn't a consistent internal organizational structure from *HR*. The *Project Implementation Team* implemented a structure that seemed to make the most sense for *Central Research*, but this did not work for all scenarios and customization was required. The stimulating condition was the *Streamlining processes*, and the releasing condition was the *Customizing processes* to enable work without accurate internal organizational structure data.

Analyzing Affordances and Associated Mechanisms

Affordances can be used as building blocks for further explanation [17]. Two affordances emerged from the case and dependencies between them were analyzed. The *Process automation* affordance relied on master data to automate research administration processes. The process of collecting publication count data was an essential precursor to the *Compliance* affordance where master data gaps were highlighted for users to fill in the correct format to obtain subsidy or funder income. These two affordances could be grouped together to assess which mechanisms were related to them as higher-level mechanisms. Both the compliance affordance and the process automation affordances were seen as being generated by a gatekeeping mechanism and a silo

mechanism. Gatekeeping is an actor's choice to decide what information and work can and cannot flow up or down an organizational hierarchy [39] whereas organizational silos trap organizational data, inhibiting the free flow of data and information resulting in the inability to realize the full potential of the data and information [2].

Assessing Explanatory Power

The mechanisms with the strongest explanatory power from the observed data collected should be chosen [17]. From the case, the gatekeeping and silo mechanisms provided the strongest explanatory power. When a department, such as *HR*, acted in a silo and was a gatekeeper of the staff master data, this inhibited other departments, such as *Central Research*, from obtaining this master data. To circumvent this, actors with a relationship with *HR* could request the missing data via spreadsheets but, without this relationship, the data needed to be captured and guessed for compliance with government and funder requirements. Similarly, for process automation, *HR* was gatekeeping the internal organizational structure master data for their own purposes that did not allow *RIS* to work for their process automation, forcing *Central Research* to customize an internal organizational structure, with help from the *Project Implementation Team*.

Conclusion

This research looked at the precursors of MDQ in an ES implementation case study. From the literature review, precursors of DQ were identified and classified. In the findings, two mechanisms were identified, a gatekeeping and a silo mechanism. The authors propose that these mechanisms could be the reasons behind precursors of MDQ.

One limitation is that the mechanisms from the case were not linked back to the precursors of MDQ from the literature review as there could be more mechanisms than were identified in the case study. Another limitation is that only interview data was used for the affordance stepwise analysis. Documentation and support calls could be added to enrich results. Recommended for future research is to map these mechanisms to each of the WSF precursors to ascertain if they are comprehensively addressing the mechanisms behind MDQ issues or if further case studies are required. Through awareness of mechanisms as precursors to MDQ, these could be addressed before ES implementations commence. Gatekeeping and silos could be identified and assessed, with initiatives put in place to foster closure, enabling departments to work together on common goals. Collective Action problems and Social Capital theories could be used by other cases for their appropriateness in assessing affordances and mechanisms. Understanding mechanisms helps organizations to proactively plan ES implementations successfully, with better MDQ outcomes and without post implementation support issues.

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